

Unequal Journeys to Motherhood: A Study on Continuum of Care and Delivery Outcomes among Tamil Women

S.K. Mercy ✉

*Assistant Professor, Department of Public Administration,
Government Arts College (Autonomous), Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India*

P. Udhayakumar

Independent Researcher, Tenkasi, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

Maternal health is a critical component of public health, and its outcomes largely depend on the continuum of care, which spans from pregnancy to childbirth and the post-pregnancy period and includes routine antenatal care, institutional delivery, and postnatal services. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends a minimum of four antenatal visits to improve delivery outcomes and promote the well-being of both mother and child. Findings from the present study reveal significant variations in delivery outcomes based on demographic factors and the extent of continuum of care received. Very difficult deliveries were reported more frequently among rural women (33%) than urban women (20%), and among those in higher maternal age groups, specifically 30–34 years (42%) and 35–39 years (33%). Smooth deliveries were more common among women who had five or more antenatal visits (36%), whose babies weighed less than 2 kg at birth (75%), and among those who experienced a very caring and supportive environment in their delivery institutions (26%). Regarding self-care practices, adequate sleep emerged as the most beneficial, with 33% of those practicing it reporting smoother delivery outcomes compared to other practices such as walking, yoga, and maintaining a healthy diet. The study also highlights the impact of medical staff behavior on delivery experiences. Very rude behavior from nurses and midwives was reported by 50% of respondents who delivered in government hospitals, which significantly affected their delivery outcomes. Fear, stress, and lack of mental preparedness were identified as the major reasons for difficult deliveries by 39% of the participants. Postnatal care was found to be crucial for long-term maternal health, as mothers with more than three postnatal visits reported fewer health issues compared to those with none or only one visit. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of continuum of care and identifies key factors that influence maternal health and delivery outcomes.

Keywords: *Maternal health, Continuum of care, Delivery outcomes, Antenatal care, Postnatal care, Partner support, Tamil women.*

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Introduction

Pregnancy and delivery are often considered a rebirth in a woman's life. While pregnancy brings joy for some women, for others it becomes a physically and emotionally challenging experience. The continuum of care remains a privilege rather than a universal reality. Various government initiatives, such as monetary benefits to promote institutional deliveries, free pregnancy supplementary kits, and government health insurance schemes, have been introduced to ensure the continuum of care that every pregnant woman deserves. Despite these efforts, the maternal journey remains difficult for some women while being comparatively smoother for others. The present study aims to identify the factors impacting delivery outcomes among women.

Various factors such as age during pregnancy, baby's birth weight, support from the partner, type of delivery institution, area of residence, mental health status, and the attitude of medical staff were analyzed to understand their influence on delivery outcomes. The study also seeks to create awareness about the importance of the continuum of care for the long-term health of women during pregnancy and after delivery. In addition, the significance of partner support in influencing delivery outcomes is highlighted in the study.

Review of Literature

In "A Global Analysis of the Determinants of Maternal Health and Transitions in Maternal Mortality" (2024) by João Paulo Souza, Louise Tina Day, Ana Clara Rezende-Gomes, Jun Zhang, Rintaro Mori, Adama Baguiya et al., published in *Maternal Health in the Perinatal Period and Beyond*, the authors identify several determinants of maternal mortality beyond biomedical causes such as hemorrhage and hypertensive disorders, like low income, limited maternal education, extremes of maternal age (<18 and >35 years), low partner involvement, poor diet, inadequate physical activity, substance abuse, poor knowledge of danger signs, lack of autonomy in health-care decisions, and limited access to quality health services as major contributors to adverse maternal outcomes.

The 2022 National Healthcare Quality and Disparities Report (USA) notes that over 25,000 deliveries in the USA annually result in severe maternal morbidity, defined as unexpected outcomes during labour and delivery with significant short- or long-term consequences.

According to the article "Maternal Health Care in India: A Reflection of 10 Years of National Health Mission on the Indian Maternal Health Scenario" (2020) by Arabinda Ghosh and Rohini Ghosh, published in *Sexual & Reproductive Healthcare*, only 51.2% of pregnant women in India receive at least four antenatal care (ANC) visits, with significant inter-state and rural-urban disparities. Kerala (90.1%), Goa (89%), Jammu & Kashmir (81.3%), and Tamil Nadu (81.1%) perform remarkably well, whereas Bihar (14.4%), Nagaland (15%), Uttar Pradesh (26.4%), and Arunachal Pradesh (26.7%) lag far behind. The rural-urban ANC gap stands at 44.8% in rural areas vs. 66.4% in urban areas, and Tamil Nadu shows the least disparity (0.3%).

The importance of maternal health literacy is emphasized by "Maternal Health Literacy (MHL) for Improved Maternal and Child Outcomes: A Scoping Review" (2025) by Aditi Chandrakar, Senthilkumar Ramasamy, Abhiruchi Galhotra, and M. Swathi Shenoy, published in the *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*. The study concludes that higher levels of maternal health literacy significantly enhance pregnancy outcomes. Mothers with higher MHL are more likely to initiate ANC earlier, attend regularly, take folic acid supplements, recognize danger signs, engage in healthy lifestyles, achieve healthier birth weights, and initiate breastfeeding.

The significance of a complete continuum of care comprising antenatal care, institutional delivery, and postnatal care (CoC) is highlighted in the study “Trends and Determinants of Maternal Health Services Utilization in India from 2015 to 2021” (2025) by Wapangjungla Longchar, Prakash Babu Kodali, and Sibasis Hense, published in Scientific Reports. The study reveals that India lags behind several Asian counterparts, such as Indonesia (69.7%), Cambodia (60%), Maldives (59.8%), and the Philippines (69.9%), with only 50% of women completing the full continuum of care.

The study identifies maternal age, parity, education, residence, wealth index, and health insurance as key determinants influencing CoC utilization. Overall, the reviewed literature underscores the critical role of antenatal visits and the completion of the continuum of care in shaping positive delivery outcomes, a pattern that is also reflected in the findings of the present study.

Methodology

The study was conducted among 100 respondents across Tamil Nadu. A purposive-cum-snowball sampling method was adopted for selecting respondents. Women who had experienced childbirth after 2005 were chosen for the study. Primary data were collected using Google Forms. For respondents with limited schooling the researchers read out the questions in Tamil, and recorded their responses. A structured questionnaire was used, covering demographic details, antenatal care practices, delivery experiences, postnatal care, and self-care behaviors during pregnancy. The collected data were analyzed using simple percentage analysis.

Results

Table 1. Residing Area vs Delivery Experience

Area	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
Rural	14	52	33
Semi Urban	50	50	0
Urban	33	47	20

Among rural respondents, only 14% reported a smooth delivery experience, while 52% experienced a moderately difficult delivery and 33% had a very difficult delivery. In semi-urban areas, 50% of respondents reported a smooth delivery, and the remaining 50% indicated a moderately difficult experience. Among urban respondents, 33% experienced a smooth delivery, 47% had a moderately difficult delivery, and 20% reported a very difficult delivery. The higher incidence of very difficult deliveries in rural areas may be attributed to several factors, including the shortage of high-risk obstetric specialists in rural hospitals, inadequate delivery preparedness, lack of emergency care facilities, lower levels of maternal health literacy, and delays in receiving timely medical assistance after the onset of labor pain.

Table 2. Age vs Delivery Experience

Age during the recent pregnancy	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
Below 20	0	100	0
20–24	67	33	0
25–29	23	55	23
30–34	25	33	42
35–39	0	67	33

Age appears to have a significant influence on delivery outcomes, and the data strongly support this. Among respondents aged below 20 years, 100% experienced a moderately difficult delivery. In the 20–24 age group, 67% reported a smooth delivery, and none experienced a very difficult delivery, indicating more favorable outcomes among younger mothers. For women aged 30–34 years, only 25% experienced a smooth delivery, while 42% had a very difficult delivery. In the 35–39 age group, none reported a smooth delivery, and 33% experienced a very difficult delivery. These findings suggest that the likelihood of complications increases with maternal age.

Table 3. Delivery Institution vs Delivery Outcome

Type of institution where delivery took place	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
Government hospital	50	33	17
Maternity hospital	17	58	25
Multispecialty hospital	30	30	40
Primary Health Centre	0	100	0

Among respondents who delivered in government hospitals, 50% reported a smooth delivery, while 33% experienced a moderately difficult delivery and 17% faced a very difficult delivery. In maternity hospitals, a majority (58%) reported a moderately difficult delivery, whereas 17% experienced smooth deliveries and 25% reported very difficult experiences. Among those who delivered in multispecialty hospitals, 40% of respondents reported a very difficult delivery. Another 30% each reported smooth and moderately difficult deliveries. In Primary Health Centres (PHCs), 100% of respondents reported a moderately difficult delivery. These findings suggest that institutional capacity, case complexity, and resource availability may influence delivery experiences across different healthcare settings.

Table 4. Antenatal Visits vs. Delivery Outcome

No of doctor visits	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
Two	9	73	18
Three	0	33	67
Four	0	50	50
Five and more	36	40	24

Antenatal visits play a crucial role in continuously monitoring the health of the pregnant woman and the development of the fetus, as well as in planning for a safe delivery. The data reveal that respondents who had five or more antenatal visits reported a higher proportion of smooth delivery outcomes (36%) compared to those who had only two (9%), three (0%), or four (0%) visits. Very difficult deliveries were more common among respondents with three antenatal visits (67%), followed by those with four visits (50%), while the proportion was comparatively lower among those with five or more visits (24%). Moderately difficult delivery experiences were noted among 73% of respondents with two antenatal visits, 33% with three visits, 50% with four visits, and 40% with five or more visits.

The findings thus indicate that adequate antenatal care contributes to better delivery preparedness, early identification of complications, and improved maternal delivery outcomes.

Table 5. Mode of Delivery vs. Delivery Outcome

Mode of delivery	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
Assisted (Forceps/Vacuum)	0	50	50
C-section	24	44	32
Normal	29	57	14

29% of those who had a normal vaginal delivery described their experience as smooth, while 24% of respondents who underwent a C-section reported the same. Among those who had assisted (forceps/vacuum) delivery, only moderately difficult (50%) and very difficult (50%) outcomes were reported, with no respondent describing the experience as smooth. Only 14% of the respondents who had a normal delivery reported a very difficult experience, indicating that normal delivery generally results in better delivery outcomes compared to other modes.

Table 6: Baby's Birth Weight vs. Delivery Outcome

Baby's birth weight	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
less than 2 kgs	75	0	25
2-3kgs	14	57	29
more than 3 kgs	25	50	25

Baby's birth weight has long been a determining factor in the delivery experience, and the findings of this study support this. Among mothers who delivered babies weighing less than 2 kg, 75% reported a smooth delivery, and only 25% experienced a very difficult delivery. In contrast, only 14% and 25% of respondents in the 2–3 kg and above 3 kg categories, respectively, reported smooth deliveries. A majority in these groups experienced moderately difficult or very difficult delivery outcomes—57% and 29% in the 2–3 kg category, and 50% and 25% in the above 3 kg category. These results indicate that higher birth weight is associated with increased delivery difficulty compared to lower birth weight.

Table 7. Self-care vs Delivery Outcome

Self-Care Practices	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
Walking	20	48	32
Yoga	30	30	40
Meditation	30	30	40
healthy diet	25	47	28
adequate rest	33	40	27

Pregnant women are generally advised to follow self-care routines such as walking, meditation, yoga, consuming a healthy diet, and taking adequate rest to ensure better delivery outcomes. Among these practices, adequate rest appears to be the most beneficial, as 33% of women who ensured sufficient rest reported a smooth delivery, and only 27% experienced a very difficult delivery. Practices such as yoga, meditation, maintaining a healthy diet, and regular walking were also associated with smooth deliveries, with 30%, 30%, 25%, and 20% of women, respectively, reporting favorable outcomes. Although a higher proportion of very difficult delivery experiences (40%) was observed among women who practiced yoga and meditation regularly, this does not imply that these practices are the least beneficial. These self-care practices remain crucial for promoting favorable delivery outcomes; however, delivery experiences are also influenced by other factors such as maternal health conditions, pregnancy-related complications, and the availability and timeliness of medical support.

Table 8. Mental Well-Being vs Delivery Experience

Mental condition	Smooth	Moderately difficult	Very Difficult
Very happy	26	47	26
Stressed	19	53	28

Mental well-being is widely recognized as an important determinant of delivery outcomes. The data reflect a similar trend among respondents who reported feeling very happy often and those who experienced frequent stress during pregnancy. Among the women who felt very happy throughout their pregnancy, 26% had a smooth delivery, and another 26% experienced a very difficult delivery. Similarly, among those who reported being stressed often, 19% had smooth deliveries while 28% experienced very difficult delivery outcomes. This indicates that while mental state does influence delivery experience, it may interact with other factors such as physical health, medical support, and pregnancy-related risks.

Table 9. Stress Relief Practices during Pregnancy vs Delivery Experience

Stress Relief Practices During Pregnancy	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
None	0	0	100
Concentrated on my other kid	0	0	100
Concentrating on my interests	0	75	25
Family support	14	71	14
Husband support	31	46	23
Not stressed	100	0	0
Listening to music	25	50	25
Prayers	50	0	50
Reading a book	100	0	0

The data reveal that 100% of women who did not practice any stress-relief methods during pregnancy and those who concentrated on their other child to cope with stress, experienced very difficult delivery outcomes.

Among women who received family support, 14% reported smooth delivery experiences and 71% reported moderately difficult deliveries. Husband's support during pregnancy played a crucial role in delivery outcomes; among women who received partner support, 31% reported smooth deliveries, 46% reported moderately difficult deliveries, and only 23% experienced very difficult deliveries. Some women found solace through prayers; among them, 50% reported smooth deliveries, while the remaining 50% experienced very difficult delivery outcomes. Notably, 100% of women who reported being not stressed during pregnancy and those who engaged in reading books as a stress-relief practice reported smooth delivery experiences. Overall, the data emphasize the importance of stress-relief practices and partner support in influencing delivery outcomes.

Table 10. Medical Staff Behavior (Doctors, Nurses, Midwives) during Delivery vs Delivery Outcome

Treatment by medical staff (doctors, nurses, midwives) during delivery	Smooth	Moderately Difficult	Very Difficult
All were careless	0	0	100
Neutral, just did their job	14	71	14
Some were careless, rude, and uninterested	20	40	40
Very caring and supportive	26	52	22

The behavior and support provided by medical staff, including doctors, nurses, and midwives, play a crucial role in determining delivery outcomes. The data show that 100% of respondents who felt they were treated carelessly reported a very difficult delivery experience. A smooth delivery outcome was most commonly reported (26%) among women who were attended to by caring and supportive staff. Among those who felt the staff were neutral and simply performed their duties, 14% reported a very difficult delivery, whereas 40% of those treated by rude or uninterested staff experienced a very difficult delivery outcome. Overall, the findings indicate that attentive and supportive medical care positively influences the delivery experience.

Figure 1. Determinants of Delivery Outcomes

Note: Delivery outcomes are classified as smooth, moderately difficult, and very difficult based on women's self-reported delivery experiences.

Table 11. Delivery Institution Type vs. Medical Staff (Doctors, Nurses, Midwives, etc.) Behavior

Type of institution where delivery took place -Medical Staff behavior (Nurses, midwives)	All were careless	Neutral, just did their job	Some were careless and uninterested	Very caring and supportive	Very rude
Government hospital	0	17	0	33	50
Maternity hospital	5	18	0	77	0
Multispecialty hospital	10	10	10	60	10
Primary Health Centre	0	0	0	100	0
Private hospital	0	50	0	50	0
Type of institution where delivery took place (Doctors' behavior)	All were careless	Neutral, just did their job	Some were careless and uninterested	Very caring and supportive	Very rude
Government hospital	0	17	33	50	0
Maternity hospital	5	14	0	82	0
Multispecialty hospital	10	10	10	70	0
Primary Health Centre	0	0	0	100	0
Private hospital	0	0	0	100	0

Government hospitals are often affected by overcrowding, shortage of personnel, inadequate medical equipment, and limited bed availability, which together create a stressful environment for both patients and staff. These systemic challenges can contribute to overworked medical personnel and result in rude or indifferent behavior toward patients. This is reflected in the findings, where 50% of respondents who delivered in government hospitals felt the staff were very rude, and only 33% reported receiving very caring and supportive treatment. In contrast, 100% of the respondents who delivered in Primary Health Centres (PHCs) reported that doctors, nurses, and midwives were very caring and supportive. A similarly high level of positive medical attention from doctors in particular was observed among those who delivered in private hospitals (100%), 82% in maternity hospitals, and 70% in multispecialty hospitals. With regard to nursing and midwifery care in particular, 77% of respondents who delivered in maternity hospitals reported very caring and supportive behavior, followed by 60% in multispecialty hospitals and only 33% in government hospitals.

Table 12. Reasons for Difficulty in Delivery

Reasons for difficulty in delivery	Percentage
No difficulty	41
Fear, stress, or lack of mental preparedness	39
lack of timely medical assistance	34
Abnormal baby position	32
Complications during Pregnancy (bleeding, High BP)	27
lack of transportation facilities	27
Baby's weight too high or too low	24
Early or overdue delivery	24
Others	24
Preexisting health conditions	17
Inexperienced or unskilled health worker	12
Poor infrastructure at the delivery facility	12

Multiple reasons were cited by respondents for experiencing difficulty during delivery. Fear, stress, or lack of mental preparedness emerged as the most commonly reported reason, mentioned by

39% of the respondents. This was followed by lack of timely medical assistance (34%), abnormal fetal position (32%), and complications during pregnancy, such as high blood pressure or bleeding (27%). Other significant reasons included lack of transportation facilities (27%), issues related to the baby's weight being too high or too low (24%), and delivery occurring earlier or later than expected (24%). Additionally, pre-existing health conditions (17%), inexperienced or unskilled health personnel (12%), and poor infrastructure at the delivery facility (12%) were also identified as contributing factors. Despite these challenges, 41% of respondents reported experiencing no major difficulty during delivery.

Figure 2. Reasons for difficulty in delivery

Table 13. Antenatal and Postnatal Check-ups by Area of Residence

Antenatal check-ups	Rural	Semi Urban	Urban
Two	29	0	31
Three	10	0	6
Four	10	0	0
Five and more	52	100	63
Postnatal check-ups	Rural	Semi Urban	Urban
NIL	0	0	19
one	10	25	31
Two	24	25	19
3 and more	67	50	31

Continuum of care is crucial for improving maternal health. It encompasses both antenatal and postnatal check-ups. The data show that five or more antenatal visits were reported by 100% of semi-urban respondents, 63% of urban respondents, and 52% of rural respondents. A minimum of four antenatal check-ups is generally associated with better delivery outcomes, including safer delivery and improved maternal and child health. Higher levels of maternal health awareness and access to healthcare facilities may explain the higher antenatal visits among semi-urban and urban women compared with rural respondents. In contrast, the pattern for postnatal check-ups differs. Three or more postnatal visits were reported by 67% of rural women, compared with 50% of semi-urban and 31% of urban respondents. The higher rate of postnatal attendance among rural women may be attributed to government monetary benefit schemes that are linked to the completion of scheduled postnatal visits, which extend up to the tenth month of the child following vaccination.

This ensures consistent monitoring and promotes better health outcomes for both mothers and infants.

Table 14. Persisting Health Issues vs Postnatal Visits

Persisting health issues	NIL	One visit	Two visits	Three or more visits
No issues	33	13	67	57
Anemia, advanced periods, fatigue, Foot pain, Back pain, Body pain, knee pain, high Blood pressure, weight issues, Emotional imbalance, postpartum depression, some itching problems, severe pain in the C-section area, Tiredness, diabetes	67	87	33	43

A higher proportion of respondents who did not have any postnatal visits (67%) and those who had only one visit (87%) continued to experience health issues such as anemia, fatigue, back and body pain, knee pain, high blood pressure, itching, C-section pain, emotional imbalance, postpartum depression, tiredness, diabetes, and abnormal weight changes in contrast, with 57% of respondents who had three or more postnatal visits who did not report any persisting health problems. Thus, the findings highlight that consistent postnatal follow-up plays a crucial role in ensuring better recovery and long-term health outcomes for mothers.

Conclusion

Completion of the continuum of care is crucial for achieving positive maternal health outcomes, reducing postpartum complications, and improving the long-term well-being of women. Yet the completion rate of the continuum of care in India remains low at around 50%, and the findings of the present study also align with this national trend. Completion of the recommended four ANC (Antenatal Care) visits was found to be lower among rural respondents compared to semi-urban and urban women, while the trend was reversed in the case of postnatal visits, which may be attributed to the fast-paced and demanding nature of urban lifestyles, which can reduce compliance with recommended postnatal checkups. Introducing special government-operated mobile PNC (Postnatal Care) clinics for new mothers can significantly enhance access, especially for urban women with time constraints and rural women with mobility issues. The study also highlights the positive impact of husband support during pregnancy. Creating awareness among partners about their role in ANC, delivery preparedness, and PNC can significantly improve maternal health outcomes.

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